

OPPORTUNITIES TO USE DISTANCE LEARNING IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract. *Today, every area of our society cannot be imagined without information technologies. In developed countries, the use of computer technologies in the process of teaching students, increasing students' knowledge, and automating all factors that shape their creative potential have been established. An improved form of this is "distance learning". Distance education has accelerated the process of globalization in the education system of the world by removing barriers to study and exchanging ideas about all reforms and innovations in the education system of Western and Eastern countries. The result of the process of globalization in the educational system is the development of distance education.*

Keywords: *innovative technologies, information technologies, independent research, distance education.*

Today, the main task of the higher education system is to train a qualified specialist. In order to prepare such a specialist, it is necessary to determine the system of demands placed on him. Educators, looking for an answer to this question, encountered a system of requirements in the following four directions:

1. Having the necessary knowledge, skills and qualifications in their field.
2. Constantly improving existing knowledge of the field independently, that is, being ready for independent education.
3. To have independent research and creativity skills to introduce innovations in the field.
4. To have the ability to plan, manage and organize one's own time.

What is required in the naturalization of a person who meets the specified system of requirements. Today, in order to reveal all the possibilities of a student's personality, it is necessary that education be oriented to the individual. For this, in the process of organizing education, it is necessary to take into account the student's abilities, needs and unique aspects [1].

Today, the interest and attention to the use of interactive methods, innovative technologies, pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process is growing day by day. One of the reasons for this is that, until now, in traditional education, students were taught to acquire only ready-made knowledge, but modern technologies teach them to search for the acquired knowledge, independently study, analyze it, and even draw their own conclusions [2]. Therefore, modern teaching methods, interactive methods, and innovative technologies have a significant role in educational institutions.

Today, blended learning is emerging as an innovation. Declan Burn says about "blended learning" (mixed education) - "this education is aimed at effective use of rich pedagogical experience". Such an approach can be based on the use of different methodologies in the presentation of information, information technologies in the organization of education and in the educational process, and the organization of traditional activities individually and in groups. Such a different approach does not tire the student and increases his motivation to study. The main issue is ensuring the compatibility of the chosen methods and achieving high efficiency at a low cost

Blended learning requires the organization of more training. The following steps should be taken into account when organizing trainings:

1. Preparation stage.
2. The stage of identifying goals.
3. Training stage.

Today, blended learning means a combination of elements of traditional full-time education and distance education. In this system, the teacher remains at the center of learning and has made extensive and effective use of the Internet. It is well known that the importance of information technologies in the educational system is incomparable. Every year, new versions of it are offered. If we look at the history of the introduction of these technologies into the educational system [3].

At the end of the 18th century, "correspondence education" appeared as a result of the introduction of regular postal service in Europe, which was available to the majority of the population. Students receive study materials by mail and have written communication with teachers. Those who determined the results of mastering, in the form of a scientific work or by passing an exam to a trusted person. Such a form appeared in Russia at the end of the 19th century. At the beginning of the 20th century, the rapid development of technologies, the appearance of radio and television brought new changes to distance education methods. The introduction of such technologies is associated with a sharp increase in social life, which has led to a multifold increase in the number of readers. Since the 50s of the 20th century, educational TV programs have been organized. But there was a serious drawback in the training conducted on radio and television, that is, the student did not have the opportunity to receive feedback. In 1969, the world's first distance education university was opened in Great Britain. The university was named "Open University of Great Britain". The reason for its name was that it was not necessary to go to the training halls very often. Such a distance learning university has created opportunities for distance learning at a low cost.

Famous universities operating on the basis of distance learning programs have emerged in foreign countries. For example, Fern Universitat in Hagen (Germany, 1974). National University of Technology USA 1984, Open University of Hagen (Germany), INTEC College Cape Town (USA), Open Business School of British Open University, National University of Distance Learning of Spain, Regional Information Network of Australia, etc. The role of the Internet ("online") and the role of telecommunications in the popularization of distance learning education. In particular, the service of Tim Berners-Lee, the scientist who created the WWW (Web) technology for people's open access to the Internet, is incomparable. Today, distance education is well-established in the United States, and its emergence dates back to the late 1970s. Many foundations of interactive learning are emerging in the world. For example, the database of the distance education center of the British Open University can be cited as an example.

At the end of the 80s of the last century, the increase in personal computer capabilities created new opportunities related to the simplification and automation of the teaching system. Computer training programs have appeared in the form of various games.

21st century computers and the Internet have made it possible for distance learning to spread quickly and in a simplified manner. The Internet has made a huge difference to radio and television. There are opportunities to communicate and interact with any student, regardless of

where he is located. The rapid spread of the Internet made it possible to move to an "online" seminar system for learning, and as a result, the distance learning system was created.

Distance learning describes two main approaches to education:

- expansion
- transformation models

In the extension model, the teaching technology is almost no different from the traditional method. The transformational model incorporates information and communication technology tools for teacher-student collaboration.

In the process of distance learning, the audience is not required to be in the auditorium all the time. Most distance learning institutions offer general classes, sometimes in the evenings or on weekends. It is not necessary for students to participate in such activities, but their participation in such activities is useful for the formation of practical skills of the listeners [4].

In recent years, another type of distance education, "webinar" (in 1998, this term was introduced into the conversation) technology has appeared. Webinar technology involves the organization of interactive training based on web technology. This technology not only conveys information to the audience, but also creates an opportunity to communicate with them (verbally, in writing), that is, it is possible to exchange ideas and express one's opinion in the form of a seminar. In other words, the education organized on the basis of the Internet network is moving to the subject-subject paradigm.

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